

Translating the Impossible: Listening, Learning, and Art

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There is no meaning, of course, only a profound and inexplicable significance; why is that not enough for me?

(John Banville, *Ghosts*, p. 95)

For Heidegger, translation and interpretation are intimately related. Translation is not the simple transference of meaning from one language to another, but involves an act of authentic thinking, or reflection. The word Heidegger uses to designate reflection, for example in *Basic Concepts* (1998; 1981), is *Besinnung*, which has the sense of being thoughtful, thinking through, remembering, and also calming down, and even regaining consciousness. And the kind of thinking or reflection Heidegger has in mind always tries to create something new, or other.

Miles Groth (2004) defines Heidegger's theory of translation in the following way: "*Translation is the event that retraces the response to language that we call thinking*" (p 121). From this it follows that the act of translating and the acts of learning about and interpreting art have many similarities.¹ For one, they are performative acts; they do something with something else, be it language, words, sound, paint, clay, or even history.² In turn, these ways of doing things are also ways of learning, since what comes about from the activity is something new or other. That is, the learner creates something that was not known to him or her by making use of what already exists.

In this paper we want to explore how the "basic" concepts of listening and translating can be seen as interrelated, and how they can have important effects on teaching and learning. We especially focus on how listening and translating are related to learning and art, and draw on our own subject areas (music education and literature) to exemplify our argument. More precisely, we will deal with poetry and music awareness, making use of our different experiences as teachers and learners. This means that our respective contributions here are quite different in tone and style, but we believe that this reflects each discipline's specificity and our individual stances regarding the aims of this article.

When it comes to the section on music education, the text takes a more practical and at the same time more subjective perspective, reflecting the discipline's focus on physically "doing" art. The section on literary study is more theoretical and wants, in contrast, to highlight the "doing" of art through reflective and analytical thinking. The contrast between the two disciplines is important since it shows how listening and translating, and the subsequent production of meaning, involve different perspectives on philosophical thought and how they can be used to promote learning. Despite, or perhaps because of, the differences between the two sections, our aim is to show that they mutually imply each other—that they, to use one of the basic concepts we examine, translate each other. Nevertheless, our overall aim is to investigate how the philosophical thinking around these concepts in Heidegger's later philosophy can illuminate and inform the interpretation and creation of art from a pedagogical perspective.³ This means, furthermore, taking into account the subject relations involved in

teaching and learning: the relations between teacher and student, but also the relations between each student and other students, which in consequence means involving the social context for learning. What is at stake in learning about and teaching art is in this instance the ability to listen—to listen to what the work of art calls us to think, and also, equally importantly, to listen to others (teachers/students) in order to grasp, question, and interpret the shared experiences of listening to the work of art under scrutiny. This, in turn, implies a creative act, an act of making, shaping, and performing in the form of, for example, music or text. It means translating by listening to the unknown, and thus, by way of translating, learning the language of the other.⁴

What does it mean to learn to interpret and/or create art? And how can we teach the skills these acts involve? What is the difference between the one who creates art and the one who experiences art?⁵ We would like to suggest that to answer these questions, the concept of translation is essential, because, as Heidegger points out, a translation is never finished; it is a process and a way of thinking (Groth, 2004, p. 121) that implies the act of listening authentically to the language of the other (be it the other as another human being or the other as a work of art), which means translating by interpreting to faithfully transpose what we hear into another language. This happens, Heidegger says, not only when we consciously translate from one language into another, but whenever we hear another human being speak to us (Groth, 2004, p. 134-135). If the act of translation is viewed with a Heideggerian eye, then we are in a sense almost always in the process of translating, because we are always already in language. Translation thus becomes the way we as human beings interpret and transfigure the world; in other words, it is how we learn, in the most basic sense of the term.⁶ Groth (2004) explains that Heidegger's philosophy of translation "implies that all use of us by language implicates us in translating, and that translating that begins with a written text is only a special case of what is going on all the time when language speaks" (p. 135). This view of translation is interesting to explore in relation to the creation and interpretation of art, and also in order to make it possible to use the process of translation in art education.

In consequence, we suggest that when it comes to learning to interpret or to create art, translation can have important pedagogical implications. In order to create we must learn, and in order to learn we must create by going back to listen to what is not there in what is; that is, we must listen to the nothing in what exists. "Da-sein means," writes Heidegger in "What Is Metaphysics?" (1993c) "being held out into the nothing" (p. 103) [*Da-sein heisst: Hineingehaltenheit in das Nichts* (Heidegger, 1976, p. 115)].⁷ That is, Da-sein is transcendence; it is beyond beings in order to be able to relate to other beings and to ourselves. In comparison, when we encounter a work of art, we encounter something completely new or other; we encounter the nothing, since the work does not provide us with meaning in and of itself. We are being held out into the nothing, without footing, being obliged to listen to the language of the work by translating it and so creating it again as something other than what it "is"; and in this way the work acquires a meaning, however tentative and provisional. The work of art becomes what it is only by being something else, by being foreign and other, through our act of translating it. In this way we learn, not only what the work of art can mean, but how to go about learning. As Heidegger puts it in *Basic Concepts*, we have to "learn 'learning'" ["*das Lernen' zu lernen*"] again (Heidegger, 1998, p. 11; Heidegger, 1981, p. 13).

Through a thoughtful, reflective translation of the work of art, truth as the truth of Being [*Sein*] appears as an unconcealment. Heidegger, in "The Origin of the Work of Art" (1993b), calls this a happening or event.⁸ The work of art thus comes into being *as* art, which means that the work at the same time reveals the truth of Being [*Sein*] as art. This movement is

similar to what happens in translating from one language into another: language is at the same time unveiled or unconcealed and hidden away or concealed—we come to learn the meaning of the words, but we do this by transforming the language, by concealing it as other. This double movement can also be seen in the context of Heidegger's essay "Building, Dwelling, Thinking" (1993a). Here Heidegger points out the etymological relatedness of building [*Bauen*] and dwelling [*Wohnen*], but also importantly shows their relation with Being [*Sein*]. Dwelling is, according to Heidegger, how human beings essentially *are* on the earth. Dwelling means being in such a way that we are in tune with our environment, which implies that I, as a subject, am already related to whatever inheres in the space in which I am. We would like to suggest that the Heideggerian sense of dwelling can be analogous to how we as teachers and students relate to art through the performative act of translating art into a learning experience.

To make the philosophical perspective outlined above more tangible, we will, in the following sections, share examples from our specific academic disciplines and describe instances where possibilities for learning inspired by Heidegger's thinking are put into educational practice. Notions of language and art from a Heideggerian perspective will be related to notions of learning. We will conclude by indicating some possibilities for teaching and learning about art from our outlined philosophical perspectives.

The Pressure of Reality: Translation, Learning and the Poetry of Wallace Stevens

How can we teach Wallace Stevens' poetry? How can we, as teachers, provide a space in which learning Stevens' poetry becomes a thoughtful and creative reflection on the essence of Stevens' work? How can we as students of Stevens' poetry at the same time be true to his words and make them our own? That is, how can we (both students and teachers) translate the work of Wallace Stevens?

In order to investigate how reading Stevens' poetry can become a philosophically relevant learning experience, I want to begin by looking briefly at Heidegger's translations of Hölderlin. In the lecture course published as *Hölderlin's Hymn "The Ister"* (1996),⁹ Heidegger's approach is one of both interpreting and translating Hölderlin, which in turn leads him to a method of philosophical reflection. He is concerned with poetry, and specifically with Hölderlin's poetry, as an instance (a happening, occurrence, *ereignis*) of language that can be said to respond to the call of Being. To respond to the call of Being involves going back to the origin, to what Heidegger calls the inception of history. This going back to listen to the inception is to listen authentically to the call of Being. According to Heidegger's remarks in his discussion of Hölderlin's poetry, this poetry, as a response to Being, goes beyond any metaphysical interpretation of Being and art, since for Heidegger Hölderlin's poetry is not concerned with symbolic language. As Heidegger (1996) puts it,

if Hölderlin's hymnal poetry is a naming, and if naming first elevates and poetizes what is named into its essence, then the river poems cannot be poems "about" rivers, in which the rivers are already familiar in their essence and are taken as images or emblems signifying something else. This is why we are claiming that Hölderlin's river poetry, indeed his hymnal poetry as a whole, is not concerned with symbolic images. This entails the wider claim that this poetic art is not metaphysical. To the extent that, according to the strict Western conception of art, art exists only as metaphysical art, Hölderlin's poetry, if it is no longer metaphysical, is no longer "art" either. The essences of art and of metaphysics are not sufficient to lend this poetry the essential space appropriate to it. If it is not metaphysical, however, then this poetry is

not “philosophy” either; for since Plato, all thinking that has been called “philosophy” is metaphysics. (p. 26)

Hölderlin’s poetry, then, according to Heidegger, consists of a naming that names the essence of what is named by elevating and poetizing it: “[W]e use the word ‘naming’ in Hölderlin’s sense. For Hölderlin, naming means something higher. ‘Naming’ means: to call to its essence that which is named in the word of poetizing, and to ground this essence as poetic word. Here, ‘naming’ is the name for poetic telling. Such telling, in being a naming, receives a unique vocation that does not allow itself to be straightforwardly transferred to other poetry or other poets” (Heidegger, 1996, p. 21). This naming, moreover, goes beyond the Western conceptions of metaphysics and art, which Heidegger holds makes it neither art nor poetry as conceived within metaphysics. Naming the essence, furthermore, is both a vanishing and an intimation, Heidegger says. With this, he suggests that Hölderlin’s poetry, as naming, is at the same time a looking into the future and a going back into the past. Thus when Hölderlin names the river in “The Ister” he is telling about the river as a journeying that both goes back into the past and forward into the future: “As vanishing, the river is underway into what has been. As full of intimation, it proceeds into what is coming. The river is a singular kind of journey, insofar as it simultaneously proceeds into what has been and what is to come” (Heidegger, 1996, p. 29). Heidegger then connects the essence of the river to his thoughts on dwelling: “Becoming homely and dwelling upon the earth are of another essence. We may approach it in giving thought to the essence of the rivers. The river is the locality for dwelling. The river is the journeying of becoming homely. To put it more clearly: the river is that very locality that is attained in and through journeying” (p. 31). Heidegger continues: “Our claim is this: the river is the locality of the dwelling of human beings as historical upon this earth. The river is the journeying of a historical coming to be at home at the locale of this locality. The river is locality and journeying” (p. 33). About this seemingly circular argument, Heidegger notes,

The said statements are always incomprehensible within a certain realm of comprehension, and there is an essential reason for this. The incomprehensibility of such statements is not grounded in some contingent lack of knowledge that would be otherwise attainable. Even those who once understand such statements are not able to understand them at any hour whatsoever. We are excluded from comprehending such statements so long as the appropriation of an essential transformation in our essence has not “occurred” [*sich “ereignet”*]. (p. 34)

In order to understand Hölderlin’s poetical telling of the river, that is, its naming, one must have transformed one’s essence—such a transformation has to have occurred. It could thus be argued that Heidegger’s remarks on Hölderlin’s poetry are an attempt to “learn” what this kind of transformation entails, while at the same time enacting such a transformation by reflecting on and translating (in Heidegger’s sense of the term) Hölderlin’s poetry. More precisely, the lecture course on Hölderlin’s hymn “The Ister” is an attempt to teach philosophy and poetry beyond metaphysics, that is, philosophy and poetry as Heidegger conceives of them. And he does this by focusing on what he considers Hölderlin’s singularity and the uniqueness of his poetry. This singularity and uniqueness make the reflection on and translation of Hölderlin’s poetry equally singular and unique, since, according to Heidegger, what can be said of Hölderlin cannot be generalized into a generic method for philosophizing or reading poetry. The singularity of Hölderlin’s poetry is what shapes the method (if one can still call it that).

However, this is far from being a novel approach to analyzing poetry. The singularity of poetry is well known among literary scholars, and it is also in many instances what shapes the teaching of poetry. Nevertheless, in the following I would like to make some remarks on Wallace Stevens by way of comparing and contrasting these remarks with Heidegger's thoughts on poetry and translation. Stevens' thoughts on poetry, or what could be called his theory or philosophy of poetry, are abundantly present in his poetic practice. My aim is to intimate what teaching Stevens can imply in terms of his poetry's singularity. I want to do this by looking at similarities and differences between Heidegger's reading of Hölderlin and a reading of Stevens' poetry, using Heidegger's thoughts on translation as an inception to teaching poetry—not forgetting the singularity of every poet and every instance of poetry.

In Stevens' work, the relation between the imagination and reality is well known. The tension between the two has been traced back to Santanaya, Emerson, and transcendentalism, and to the romantics, especially Coleridge, and by extension to Kant and German idealism.¹⁰ In the essay "The Noble Rider and the Sound of Words," from his collection *The Necessary Angel: Essays on Reality and the Imagination*, Stevens (1953) describes the relation between the imagination and reality in the following way: "It is not only that the imagination adheres to reality, but, also, that reality adheres to the imagination and that the interdependence is essential" (p. 33). In relation to this, Stevens notes about the function of the poet:

The poet refuses to allow his task to be set for him. He denies that he has a task and considers that the organization of *materia poetica* is a contradiction in terms. Yet the imagination gives to everything that it touches a peculiarity, and it seems to me that the peculiarity of the imagination is nobility, of which there are many degrees. (p. 33)

This nobility of the imagination, Stevens says, is not something that can be fixed and determined: "as a wave is a force and not the water of which it is composed, which is never the same, so nobility is a force and not the manifestations of which it is composed, which are never the same.... It is the imagination pressing back against the pressure of reality" (p. 35-36). Here Stevens points to what he calls the peculiarity of the imagination, and how this peculiarity can be seen as the nobility of the imagination. This nobility is precisely the force of the interplay between and interdependence of reality and the imagination. The peculiarity of the imagination can also, I suggest, be compared to the singularity of poetry—every poem is peculiar, just as is every signature of one's name; it is always the same but each time unique. The poem, just like the signature, calls for translation. And the translation has to take into consideration the peculiarity of the imagination and the generality of reality.

In order to begin an explication of the peculiarity of Stevens' poetry, his poem "The Snow Man" from his *Collected Poems* (1990, p. 9-10) can serve as an example:

One must have a mind of winter
To regard the frost and the boughs
Of the pine-trees crusted with snow;

And have been cold a long time
To behold the junipers shagged with ice,
The spruces rough in the distant glitter

Of the January sun; and not to think
Of any misery in the sound of the wind,
In the sound of a few leaves,

Which is the sound of the land
Full of the same wind
That is blowing in the same bare place

For the listener, who listens to the snow,
And, nothing himself, beholds
Nothing that is not there and the nothing that is.

Just as Heidegger insists on transforming one's essence in order to understand what Hölderlin tells about the river, so Stevens here prescribes, by the words "One must," how one must be in order to genuinely (or authentically, to invoke Heidegger) see, hear and feel the winter.¹¹ One must become winter in order to perceive the essence of winter, and one must become nothing to behold "Nothing that is not there and the nothing that is." This becoming nothing can be compared to Heidegger's description of "Being held out into the nothing" in "What Is Metaphysics?" which implies transcending the everyday world so as to become open to the unknown, the nothing, which is the essence of what Stevens calls reality; that is, the force in the tension between the imagination and reality.

Stevens' imperative that "One must have a mind of winter" also carries with it a call to learn: one must learn to become winter; one must learn to become nothing to behold it. The transformation of one's essence required in order to be able to perceive winter must be learned. And this learning comes about by paying attention to Stevens' poetry as naming, or rather, to heeding to and translating the peculiarity of Stevens' poetry.

In one of Stevens' most well known long poems, "Notes Toward a Supreme Fiction" (Stevens, 1990, p. 380-408), the question of how a supreme fiction can be conceived is set up through a master poet/teacher speaking to an aspiring poet/student. The poem begins with the teacher telling the student that he "must become an ignorant man again / And see the sun again with an ignorant eye / And see it clearly in the idea of it" (p. 380). As in "The Snow Man," we have here a question of learning how to transform one's essence to be able to listen to what the poem says. One has to be in the right mood, as it were, or *Stimmung*, to use Heidegger's term. In Stevens' terms, one must have a "mind" of winter or the sun; one must become "ignorant" to be able to hear the nothing that is.¹² Stevens' poetry thus explicitly stages what Heidegger finds in poetry such as Hölderlin's. Both Heidegger and Stevens are concerned with translating the experience of being and/as art—all their differences set aside. They do this through two different modes of translation—Heidegger through philosophy, Stevens through poetry. However, they both stress the need to transform one's essence to become in tune with the peculiarity of the specific instance of poetry or philosophy one is dealing with. In both Heidegger and Stevens, then, there is a question of learning again; of going back to learn learning again by listening, and so translating what one hears.

Given the notions proposed above, some possibilities for teaching and learning about Stevens' poetry could be the following: Teaching Stevens from a Heideggerian perspective can focus on the transformation of oneself in learning, on the concept of naming, and on the singularity or peculiarity of works of art and poetry. It can also focus on translation as the translation of reality by the imagination, and on the reader's translation of poetry into a new reality—a new language. By beginning with the nothing and emphasizing the non-meaning of the poem that the teacher has chosen to read with the students, each student can be encouraged to listen to the poem via the basic concepts of Stevens' poetry. The students and the teacher will be obliged to learn again, even to learn learning again, since the learning of the poem is as

unique and singular as the poem itself. In reading the chosen poem, each member of the class will have to become ignorant again and work to transform his or her mind to be able to hear the poem authentically, and thus build a translation from dwelling with the poem. This work of translation can become an *ereignis* that will cause the poem to take on meaning and become unconcealed—the poem’s significance will be made to sound through a thoughtful listening to it. And listening as translation will provide the poem with a language that can be read, understood and shared—a language that can be learned, and so communicated and translated again within the process of reading and listening to Stevens’ poetry. This sense of teaching and learning about Stevens’ poetry is, in other words, a form of aesthetic communication, using the concepts of translation and listening both performatively and conceptually, to learn again from the nothing that is.

Listening as Musical Dwelling—Translation and Learning a Language of Art

What can it mean—being “in tune” with our environment? What can it mean—Being as music? The aim of this section of the article is to investigate how reasoning about Being and art in Heidegger’s later works can be used for investigating possibilities for arts education. From a musical perspective, a work of art can *be* a world where music making can take place. Performers, listeners, and composers dwell in the world music creates. This kind of dwelling can best be characterized as “improvisation,” which includes creating what is conveniently at hand as well as cultivating, that is, discovering and expressing at the same time. Thus, it could be said that dwelling “transforms the space in which one dwells” (Benson, 2003, p. 32). A work of art can also be an opening to the world, something that “strikes” us and makes our history change, and offers a way of being (Heidegger, 1993b; Leijonhuvud & Ferm Thorgersen, forthcoming). In consequence we have to ask ourselves: How can we offer our students this kind of Being that dwells? How can we offer them a way to be struck by music as art? How can we offer a way for their histories to change?

Our reading of Heidegger’s later philosophy suggests that listening is an essential, performative act within the possibility of being as art. Listening is an essential action in all musical ways of being that human beings take part in as active musicians, composers, and listeners. As we stated in the beginning of the article, being as art is related to translation and interpretation, two concepts that are intimately related with one another. From a Heideggerian perspective, translation involves an act of authentic thinking—or reflection—in which something new is created. In this section I want to give an example of what Being as music can be, and try to show what I have learned from listening to and translating my experience of music, and still learn when being struck by music. The first person perspective in this part of the article is chosen to provide the reader with a possibility of understanding the process from within.

Through an act of listening authentically to a piece of music that has followed me for almost 40 years, I try in this text to translate my inner understanding of Heidegger’s thinking about music as an opening to the world and about learning art. The example can be seen as a description of how conceptual knowledge can be developed from an approach to the musical world that is expressed as an engaged and deeply rooted immersedness in the world (Pio, 2009, p. 139-166). I will try to transpose my reflections, my responses to the music, and also my learning about music by going into the dimensions of calming down, making, interpreting, and handling the world by being as art and being as other. I ask, What have I learned about music, what have I learned about learning, and what have I learned through and about the language, or expression, of the other? By extension, this understanding can hopefully provide some useful implications for teaching music.

Some time before the listening activity I decided which song to focus on. The song is a blues-waltz within the jazz genre recorded by Swedish jazz musicians—playing the drums, vibraphone, piano, and horns—with the famous jazz singer Monica Zetterlund. This particular recording from the 60s by Owe Törnqvist has been played in my home since I was a little girl, and it has functioned as an opening to the world for me. It changed my history. The lyrics are in Swedish, and the song is called *Mister Kelly*. The singer in the song is betrayed by Mister Kelly, who is visiting the same pub where the blues is being played with his new girl. It should be noted that the two “languages” of the piece, music and lyrics, are intimately interwoven; they influence and underline each other, and as such create a shared meaning. They are separated here to let the theoretical analysis be more nuanced.

From the time I decided to listen to this particular song in my authentic listening, it frequently presented itself in my mind, and more and more frequently the closer the day of listening came. With the presence of the song in my mind, I mostly heard and felt the lyrics, the phrasing, and the tunings of the singer, together with the saxophone “licks,” which I know by heart. I also experienced the feeling of being abandoned. Being in the music also influenced my being-in-the-world in my daily life.

On the day of the listening session I tried to create a setting that would allow me to listen to what the work of art, the song recorded in the style of Swedish jazz of the sixties, called me to think. I attempted to create a setting where I could calm down, listen to the unknown, and reflect creatively. I was alone at home, lying on the sofa with my eyes closed. I directed myself in an open way toward the music and listened to the song four times. Between each listening I made notes on my computer. I really felt that the rest of the world was bracketed; the music opened the world to me once more.

In the first listening session my directedness was toward the horns, the vibraphone, and the piano. I had never before noticed, or embodied, the vibraphone in my “everyday” listening to the song. The timbre of the brass horn harmony and the expressions of the bass-trombone (together with the saxophone’s long notes and the vibraphone’s timbre) are an important part of the characteristics of the song. Through my reflected listening I understood that this sound, or the feeling that the sound offers, is something that I have had in my mind, functioning as a model, in different musical settings, but that I did not exactly know what it consisted of. Another thing that the first listening made me aware of was why I have always loved the sound of a salient bass-trombonist. When it came to my directedness toward the piano and the vibraphone, I became aware that the vibraphone played fill-ins in the first verse, and the piano in the second. In the following verse the saxophone had that function, which was no surprise to me. I understand now that I have learned much about “taking turns” in music by listening to this song, and I had also created a model for how music in this style should be sounding. Every time I hear a new version of this song, I translate and interpret it based on this specific recording as a starting-point. The timbre, the phrasing, the tuning, and the instrumentation have contributed to my experience of the song, and also the other way around—the recorded piece as a “whole” has influenced my learning of musical parameters. Consequently, my experience of the music is important to my way of being in the (musical) world.

In my second listening session, it was impossible to bracket out the first one, though I wanted to listen to the saxophone and the singer specifically. I decided to turn my directedness to the saxophone first, since the singer is more complicated, as she uses both musical and spoken language. The saxophone part is so familiar to me that it was hard to listen to the language of

the other. I know every note, phrasing, and tuning. I sense how I can complement the singer and contribute to the atmosphere of being abandoned. In my listening, trying to understand the other, I translate this experience into a mix of feelings of anger and sadness. At the same time it is impossible not to listen to the contrast that the phrasing of the singer creates. The feeling of the laid-back stance of the singer and the sense of contrast is obvious and is embodied within me. I have learned the function of “fill-ins” and how they can be used to express feelings. I also recognize that the way of playing and combining the notes is something that I have tried to make my own when playing saxophone. I have tried to transpose the expressions onto other settings in creating my musical language together with others. The expression concerns the intervals between the notes: which ones should be “under pitch” and which “on pitch,” which notes in the phrase should be “after time” and which “on time,” which should be long and which should be short, and what saxophone sound should be used on different occasions. I have learned where my space of playing as opposed to silence is, where my space for “licking” as opposed to “back-grounding” is, etc. And finally, I have learned how I, as a saxophonist, can contribute to the musical expression as a whole. By taking part in the work of art (through reflected listening, translation of musical structures, tensions and acoustics, and emotional responses), existence is taking place: through my involvement with the work of art, I come to dwell in the (musical) world.

In the third listening session I concentrated on the singer’s musical-verbal language. Listening to the singer was even harder than listening to the saxophone. But when listening, what I heard is that Zetterlund uses all her voice, all variations of her voice, as a musical instrument. She does this so as to translate the message of the song, the sense of unhappy love and abandonment. But of course, her translation is always related to the interaction with all the other musicians. She varies between and combines lightness and darkness, being-in-tune with “blueness,” clearness with humbleness, being laid back with being even more laid back, exact timing with pushing forward, heaviness with lightness, straightness with vibrato, roughness with fragility—all in combination with the lyrics. Through these listening activities, it has become clear that I have always tried to translate her expression into my singing when singing in a similar style. But I can’t handle all the dimensions of her voice, which becomes very clear in my translation of my reflected listening into written words. I know that I am not a very good singer, but it becomes clear how complex it is to be able to sing like this woman. I also translate her singing into life in general, into love and breaking up and betrayal. I experience myself in different roles in situations like this by feeling the singer together with the musicians and how they “speak” to me—being as others. I sense the feelings of the betrayer and the betrayed, and the music gives me tools for handling and empathizing with the different roles.

In the fourth and last listening session I tried to listen to “the whole” of the recorded work of art, which also includes listening to what is not there. It became clear how the musicians together translate the message of the song into a common expression, or language. But it also became obvious how they listen to the language of “the others,” and try to respond to what they think the others express in their different instrumental-musical languages, how they respond to and complete and deepen the others’ expressions. All the four listening sessions have made it clear to me that a piece of music, as art, expression, impression, parameters (e.g. form, harmony, timbre, tension, dynamics), constitutes a work of art that functions as an opener to the world learned as musical “wholes” in different settings or styles. The parts are combined and experienced in different ways together with the “gaps” between the musical parameters, as well as between the musicians and the listeners.

All my life I have been dwelling in those kinds of musical expressions or spaces. I have listened, translated, and acted in the (musical) world. My example here takes place in an individual setting, but the learning of the work, that is, the processes of translating it, took place in different situations, mostly in the company of other human beings. I have also been exposed to music in many other ways in which the music, as well as my ability to translate it, has been limited and diminished in different ways and for different reasons. What I have learned about learning music through authentic listening is to have a deeper understanding of how important, and hard, it is to offer learners musical spaces for dwelling in which calming down and reflection are combined in perfect balance, where learners have the chance to develop what the work of art calls them to think. Spaces where they have the chance to listen to the unknown, making, shaping, and composing music through translation, and so finding their own musical language, can help them handle the world and make them feel like musical beings. We underline the weight of creating such places in the classroom, as well as in all one-to-one teaching sessions of music.

Final Words

In this paper, we have tried to examine the aesthetic space in which teachers and students find themselves and how this space can be associated with Heidegger's idea of translation—that is, how translation is related to dwelling as the interrelatedness of human beings and space from an aesthetic-pedagogical perspective. This is a space where creativity as cultivating takes place, and it entails translating as learning. Each subject in this space must be encouraged to find his or her own way of belonging authentically, or as Heidegger says in *Basic Concepts*, “We must listen our way into that place where we ourselves belong” [*Es gilt hineinzuhören in das, wohin wir selbst gehören*] (Heidegger, 1998, p. 16; Heidegger, 1981, p. 20). In this space, teachers and students are engaged in the ongoing process of translating each other, and so are learning from one another, either by some kind of aesthetic expression (such as music or poetry), or by translating, or, *de facto*, interpreting a work of art. In order for each student to find the place in which he or she belongs authentically, the teacher must serve as an example and provide a path for the students to follow, but also to stray from, since straying implies listening to what is unknown and is presently not “there.” This straying, however, only occurs within the aesthetic space in which learning and/as translating can take place.

The two last parts of the paper are meant to mutually imply each other, so that the phenomenological listening to music in the last section of the paper could inform how listening to poetry could be staged. Similarly, the section dealing with Stevens' poetry could function as a way into the subjective, phenomenological experience of authentic listening in order to learn (again) what the work of art calls us to think.¹³

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Notes

¹ The idea that translation is related to learning can be compared to Bowden & Marton's (1998) notion of transfer: "Anything you learn, you must make use of in other situations. You can never re-enter the very situation which gave birth to learning. Transfer is involved in every instance of learning; questions of transfer are simply questions of learning" (p. 25).

² We use the word "performative" here in the Austinian sense to indicate how art, learning about art, and creating art are activities that make something happen by being staged, as in for example saying "I promise" or saying "Yes" to the one you are marrying. These examples are expressions in which the expression in itself signifies the doing of an action (Austin, 1975).

³ It is perhaps interesting to note the interrelatedness of music and poetry from a philosophical perspective as deriving from the arts of the muses. According to OED the etymology of music reads as follows: "ancient Greek *μουσική* art presided over by the Muses, especially poetry sung to music, use as noun (short for *μουσική τέχνη*; compare classical Latin *ars musica*) of feminine of *μουσικός* relating to the Muse or Muses (applied generally to artistic culture, poetry, etc., but also spec. to music)."

⁴ Miles Groth (2004) notes that hearing [*hören*] in Heidegger goes beyond merely auditory listening: "For Heidegger, hearing is belonging to (*Gehören*) what language says" (p. 130).

⁵ Discussing the poetry of Wallace Stevens, Simon Critchley (2005) notes concerning this relation that "the imagination is a power over external objects, or the transformation of the external into the internal through the work of subjective creation, a creation that is given sensuous form and is therefore rendered external in the work of art, the poem. I take it that this is what Hegel means when he speaks of art being born of the spirit and then reborn in being aesthetically regarded. Art is born twice" (p. 25). Critchley is referring to Hegel's *Introductory Lectures on Aesthetics* (1993), p. 4.

⁶ In Heidegger's perhaps most extensive account of his thoughts on education, published as "Heidegger on the Art of Teaching" (2002), he notes concerning the thinkers of the past that "those thinkers are the rhetors of being. Our relation to tradition must be a hearing, or rather, a rehearing of thought's oration.... We need to hear the words, hear their oratory, hear their metaphors as for the first time" (p. 37).

⁷ This can also be compared to what Heidegger says about the university in "Heidegger on the Art of Teaching" (2002): "As a mustering into appearance, the essence of education is ... inextricably bound to the meaning of being [*Sinn des Seins*] with the result that the university emerges as a clearing [*Lichtung*] in which the relation between teacher and student takes on different shapes and forms. In a movement of transcendence, *Dasein* is torn and dislocated from its world by entry into the clearing of the university. It loses its substance, which stands constant and sturdy beneath the daily flux of moods and petty duties that preoccupy" (p. 35).

⁸ See for example p. 196. For an explication of Heidegger's developed thoughts on event or happening as appropriation [*Ereignis*], see for example Heidegger (2009).

⁹ I have chosen this work by Heidegger because it forms an analysis of poetry that is relevant

to my thoughts on reading Stevens' poetry and also contains an extensive elaboration on translation.

¹⁰ Bart Eeckhout (2001) discusses how critics have traced the influence of different philosophical schools on Stevens' poetry, and argues that the most tangible influence comes from Nietzsche and Coleridge.

¹¹ J. Hillis Miller (1990) points out that Stevens poetizes rivers in two late poems, "Metaphor as Degeneration" and "The River of Rivers in Connecticut": "Stevens sees being as a river, hidden behind all the appearances that tell of it, and yet flowing everywhere, through all space and time, and through all the contents of space and time. In these two poems he gives his most succinct expression of his apprehension of being" (p. 46).

¹² In his essay "Stevens' Poetry of Being" (1990) J. Hillis Miller shows the importance of the nothing in Stevens' poetry. The nothing, Miller points out, is what is—that is, it is being. It is the ground without ground for existence, and thus for both the real and the imagination.

¹³ An earlier version of this text was presented at the 12th International Conference on Philosophy of Education, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia, 28th to 31th July 2010.